

**National
Coordination Point
Research Data
Management**

Collaboration in research Trust is not enough

**A blogseries on issues and solutions
in data sharing in collaboration**

lcrdm task group: 'Policy and guidelines for collaboration on research data'

Thanks to the members of the task group

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Why a task group on policy and collaboration, how it started

- Round table session during Masterclass Research Support, okt. 2018 in Utrecht
- “ICT Utopia voor onderzoekers” report by Vals Plat on behalf of SURF

Conclusions:

- Collaboration across institutes important
- Barriers for inter-institute collaboration too high
- Responsibility for data security too much with researchers

Approach

Interviews with researchers and supporting staff

- Selecting use cases
- Develop interview script
- Do the interviews

- Analysis of the interview reports (brainstorm sessions)
- Write blogs in teams

Data sharing in collaboration: issues, barriers and suggestions

Conclusions

- Simple trust between partners is no longer sufficient
- Increasing regulations and requirements by funders, governments and institutes
- requirements and regulations are not coordinated with each other
- public-private partnerships
- need for standardised storage and data-exchange infrastructure

Recommendations

- Joint policy by research institutions
- Better support collaboration from the very beginning of the project
- Legal support
- Secure collaborative infrastructure

References

<https://communities.surf.nl/artikel/informatiebeveiliging-en-research-kloof-tussen-beleid-en-uitvoering>

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/privacy-control-compliance-marlon-domingus/>

ICT utopia voor onderzoekers, onderzoeksrapport door Vals Plat i.o van SURFnet. April 2017
<http://www.cs.uu.nl/docs/vakken/b1ois/werkcollege/ICTutopiaVoorOnderzoekers.pdf>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4066572#.X5au-INKhTa>

Discussion

- Priorities of the recommendations?
- Did we miss anything?
- Will differences in “Risk Appetite” prevent alignment of policies
- How to contact researchers at an early stage?
- Do we need more legal advisors or better documentation, templates and self service?
- Will Virtual Research Environments bring a solution? Not just a technical challenge (<https://www.surf.nl/oplossingen-voor-online-onderzoeksomgevingen>)